

STOP-IT

InfraRisk-CP **User's guide**

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InfraRisk-CP User's guide

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SUMMARY

The current document serves as a manual for the InfraRisk-CP tool. Additional information can be found in D4.2 report. It is noted that this is the first version of the InfraRisk-CP manual. Updated versions will be released when available.

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SINTEF

DELIVERABLE AUTHOR(S)

Ingrid Selseth (SINTEF)
Rita Ugarelli (SINTEF)

QUALITY ASSURANCE

Eivind Okstad
Jørn Vatn

SINTEF
NTNU

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

CI:	Critical infrastructure
CP:	Cyber Physical
Pr(CIE):	Probabilities (worst case) for each of the consequence dimensions
RIDB:	Risk identification data base
RIF:	Risk factors
RRM:	Risk reduction measures
RRMD:	Risk reduction measures data base
SCF:	Societal critical functions

1 Introduction

InfraRisk-CP assists the identification and prioritization of cyber-physical threats (CP) against water systems as critical infrastructures (CI), and it supports the generic risk assessment.

With InfraRisk-CP the user can list main events and generic event-scenarios of relevance to the own water system and then enter information to categorize and prioritize risks in a structured way. InfraRisk-CP also allows to:

- Make linkages between safety critical functions (SCF) or system assets, and the main events as basis for criticality assessment
- Produce risk pictures in risk matrixes per consequence category, or overall.

The tool is independent of any network modelling tools, i.e. it does not depend on EPANET, FTA/BDA representations, but information from such can be applied.

The tool is built having in mind the so called "Bow-Tie method", see Figure 1

▼ The Model Bow – tie Method

Figure 1: The Bow-Tie model

A 'bowtie' is a diagram that helps to visualize the risk with in an easy-to-understand picture. The diagram is shaped like a bow-tie, with the TOP undesired event in the middle (what is called Main event in InfraRisk-CP) and creating a clear differentiation between the **threats** (a possible direct cause for the top event), **consequences** (results of the top event directly ending in loss or damage) and the **barriers/RRMs** (any measure taken which acts against some undesirable force or intention) which can be proactive and/or reactive.

The Fault trees (FT) can be used to identify the possible ways by which an undesired event may arise from threats, while the event trees (ET) allow exploring the possible consequences following that event.

2 Installing the InfraRisk-CP tool

Install the InfraRisk-CP tool by unzipping the program (.accdb) and data file (.inr) to a folder at your PC and open the data file when starting the program. Use the InfraRiskCP_RIDBdata.inr found in the ZIP-file. The tool is designed for Windows OS and is to be used with Microsoft® Access®.

Figure 2: Installation/unzipping the file

InfraRisk-CP comprises two separate files:

InfraRiskCP.accdb: This is the program file. In addition to visual basic code it contains data tables with predefined codes, hierarchical structures for assets and events and so one.

InfraRiskCP_RIDBdata.inr: This is the data file with all risk elements defined in the STOP-IT risk identification database (RIDB). It is recommended to use the original InfraRiskCP_RIDBdata.inr file as a master file. When creating a new Project, InfraRisk-CP will always include the risk elements from this master file. Hence, upon an Update of the InfraRisk-CP program, the master file will always contain the most recent Update of the generic risk elements. Managing the various project files is discussed later on.

3 Using the InfraRisk-CP tool

The welcome window is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The welcome window

The top menu:

- File The File menu in Access
- Edit events The Edit main event - window in InfraRisk-CP for conducting analysis (see Figure 4)
- Analysis Two types of analysis: Risk Matrix views and Top risk events
- Reports Rank or List all the SCFs, and Print events by specifying a filter (SQL)
- Configuration Edit the risk matrix, quality matrix or delivery matrix and change ranges for attack frequency and/or success probability of an attack
- Project Open/save an existing project, or start a New project and specify a new Project file name (*.inr). The latter will be based on the RIBD_Master.inr (81 records).

Edit main events is the main window in InfraRisk-CP. Figure 4 shows the main window of the tool, as well as the steps to be performed to characterize a main event.

InfraRisk-CP (Level 1 of analysis)

Figure 4: The main window

3.1 How to characterize a main event

With reference to Figure 4, the information to be provided at each step are described below:

1. Describe site-specific scenario or import generic scenario descriptions from the RIDB (D3.2, 2018). Start a new record based on a RIDB-scenario (or others) by clicking "Copy event" and then edit Event ID to "site".
2. Categorize the Main event in four levels by: Add "New event" or "Change event" and select from the hierarchy.
3. Define "Type" of event (Destruction, Interruption, Manipulation, Pollution, Interruption of service) and the relation to "Cyber" (drop down lists).
4. Add affected SCFs or Assets for the risk scenario (select from the hierarchy). Add type and strength of relation between the SCF/Asset and the main event (drop down). State whether the SCF/Asset occurs Before/After the main event, or both prior to and after the main event (drop down), affecting an initiating event or barrier function, respectively. A last option is "Threat'nd", that is the SCF/Asset is threatened by the Main event itself.
5. Carry out frequency assessments of the Main event and relate to consequences. Specify physical or cyber related frequency by clicking the "?"

6. Identify vulnerabilities or risk influencing factors (drop down). Indicate whether the vulnerability or risk influencing factors act before or after the main event, or both prior to and after the main event (drop down). Add value according to drop down list for the related category.
7. Assess probabilities (worst case) for each of the consequence dimensions.
8. Select the consequence class for the respective consequence dimension. The risk colour for each consequence dimension is then viewed, as it appears in the risk matrix.
9. Describe Causes behind the event as basis for risk reduction measures (free text).
10. Tick of the relevant Risk reduction measures taken from the RRMD by clicking the magnifying glass symbol. Choose expected "Risk reduction effect" from the drop-down list (Low, Medium, High) and observe "Risk w/RRM" on the screen.

When you are done with the assessment and start treating the risks by looking at RRM, then you can either prevent the event to happen (e.g., with better maintenance) - implementing actions that reduce the effect of sources of risks on the BEFORE (left) side of the bow-tie - or mitigate it (e.g., providing alternative water source to the population...) - by mitigating the impact on the AFTER (right) side of the bow-tie, or both.

4 Example of use

InfraRisk-CP comes with 81 pre-defined events; these are listed in Annex A Table 2. The original events are copied from the RIDB in WP 3.2, D3.2. These may be used as a starting point when you want to create your own local event. The risk reduction measures are copied from RRMD in WP 4.3, D4.3.

4.1 Step 1 Describe scenario

Describe site-specific scenario or import generic scenario descriptions from the RIDB. Start a new record based on a RIBD-scenario (or others) by clicking "Copy event" and then edit Event ID to "site".

Select the event you want to change/edit (or Add a new event from scratch) by using the following sub-functions under Edit events: Edit specific assets/SCFs, Edit specific event types, set a SQL-search, or Select event by description. A last option is just using the record counter (in MSAccess; in lower left corner) moving through the whole database. After selected the event, you create your local copy of this event by pressing the button "Copy event". A window appears and your are asked to enter a new Event identifier (Event ID), see Figure 7. We suggest you keep the original event number ID from the RIBD and add your own unique text to this.

A list of the events (from "Select event by description") are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Events listed by description

Assume we want a local version of event ID 66 in Figure 6 instead of creating a new event.

Scenario description of ID 66: External attacker generates a physical caused manipulation of pump affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue

4.2 Step 2 Categorize the Main event

Categorize the Main event in four levels by: Add "New event" or "Change event" and select from the hierarchy.

No step 2 is performed in this example.

Figure 6: Event ID 66

Figure 7: New event identifier

Note that any identifier may be used, but it is recommended to include the event ID number from the generic RIDB to ensure traceability.

4.3 Step 3 Define type of event

Define "Type" of event (Destruction, Interruption, Manipulation, Pollution, Interruption of service) and the relation to "Cyber" (drop down lists).

Since we copied an event, we will keep the definition of type of event. See list of levels in Annex A Table 3.

4.4 Step 4 Add affected SCF Assets

Add affected SCFs or Assets for the risk scenario (select from the hierarchy). Add type and strength of relation between the SCF/Asset and the main event (drop down). State whether the SCF/Asset influences the before or the after the main event (drop down), i.e. affecting the initiating event or barrier function, respectively.

As default the SCF C127 is included in this example. Any other affected SCFs are selected from the hierarchy. For this example we will use the SCFs in Table 1. See the complete list of SCFs in Annex A Table 7.

Figure 8: The hierarchy of SCFs

Table 1: Examples of SCFs

SCF	BeforeOrAfter	Importance
C127	Before	R60
C12C	Before	R40
C128	Before	R40
C122	Threat'nd	V40
C12D	Before	R60

The window below the SCFs will contain a description of the selected SCF:

C127: Critical infrastructure, remaining (C); Water and sewage systems (1); Drinking water network; Pump

C12C: Critical infrastructure, remaining (C); Water and sewage systems (1); Drinking water network; Valve

C128: Critical infrastructure, remaining (C); Water and sewage systems (1); Drinking water network; Sensor

C122: Critical infrastructure, remaining (C); Water and sewage systems (1); Drinking water network; Control system

C12D: Critical infrastructure, remaining (C); Water and sewage systems (1); Drinking water network; Buildings

State whether the SCF/Asset affects the before or the after of the main event:

- | | |
|--------------|---|
| 1. Before | Prior to main event |
| 2. After | After main event |
| 3. B+A | Both prior to and after main event |
| 4. Threat'nd | The SCF is threatened by the main event |

"BEFORE" is referring to the main event affecting on assets or systems of such as a potential source of risk by increasing the frequency of-, or bringing the top event to happen (the left side of the bow-tie; Figure 1)

"AFTER" is referring to effects of the main event at the consequence side, or more precisely, affecting barriers/safety functions that may prevent or mitigate one or more of the different consequence dimensions of the top event (the right side of the bow-tie; Figure 1).

Select importance (strength of relation between the SCF/Asset and the main event):

- | | |
|---------|---|
| 1. I100 | Loss of SCF is initiating the event in the scenario |
| 2. B100 | SCF acts as a complete barrier |
| 3. R90 | SCF is very important for the scenario |
| 4. R60 | SCF is important for the scenario |
| 5. R40 | SCF is medium important for the scenario |
| 6. R15 | SCF is not very important for the scenario |
| 7. R05 | SCF is hardly important for the scenario |
| 8. W90 | SCF is very vulnerable wrt the main event |
| 9. W60 | SCF is vulnerable wrt the main event |
| 10. W40 | SCF is medium vulnerable wrt the main event |
| 11. W15 | SCF is not very vulnerable wrt the main event |
| 12. W05 | SCF is hardly vulnerable wrt the main event |

wrt with respect to

The figures in the codes listed above determine how important the SCF is with respect to a given scenario. This is again used to rank the importance of each SCF with respect to the total risk contribution. The letters in front of the numeric value (I,B,R or W) are only used to get better understanding of how the SCF influences the risk scenario. In the same way the BEFORE/AFTER codes are only used to improve the understanding of the scenario, and act as documentation to support frequency and consequence assessments, see steps 5, 7 and 8 in the following.

4.5 Step 5 Add frequency assessments

Carry out frequency assessments of the Main event and relate to consequences. Specify physical or cyber related frequency by clicking the "?"

Frequency: choose 1 of 5 predefined frequencies:

- | | |
|------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1. Very unlikely | less than once pr 100 years |
| 2. Remote | Once pr 10-100 years |
| 3. Occasional | Once pr 1-10 years |
| 4. Probable | 1-10 times pr year |
| 5. Frequent | More than once a month |

Figure 9: Specify physical or cyber related frequency

To assess the frequency of a successful attack to the water distribution system the following approach is followed:

1. To find the frequency of an attack attempt (sometimes referred to as likelihood of threat happening) a set of questions is provided (see Chapter 5)

2. For each question there is a predefined list of answers, where each answer is associated with a score. A low score means that there is not much support for an attack attempt and a high score means that there is support for expecting an attack attempt.
3. The scores are aggregated to give a total score for the frequency of an attempt
4. To transform the score to a frequency number a low value, f_L , and a high value f_H are defined. f_L represents the frequency of an attack attempt if all scores for the attack attempt questions have the lowest possible values, and f_H represents the frequency of an attack attempt if all scores have the highest possible values. As default values $f_L = 1/100$ (one per hundred years) and $f_H = 20$ (20 per year) are used. The user of InfraRisk-CP may change these values, but they remain constant for all assessments.
5. To find the probability of the success of an attack attempt (sometimes referred to as likelihood of threat succeeding) another set of questions is provided
6. For each of these questions there is also a predefined list of answers, where each answer is associated with a score. A low score means that there is not much support for a successful attack attempt and a high score means that there is support for expecting the attack attempt to succeed.
7. To transform the score to a probability number a low value, p_L , and a high value p_H are defined. p_L represents the probability of a successful attack attempt if all scores have the lowest possible values, and p_H represents the probability if all scores have the highest possible values. As default values $p_L = 1/100$ and $p_H = 0.5$. The user of InfraRisk-CP may change these values, but they remain constant for all assessments.
8. To find the frequency of a successful attack attempt, the frequency of an attack attempt is multiplied with the probability of success.

4.6 Step 6 Identify vulnerabilities

Identify vulnerabilities or risk influencing factors (drop down). Indicate whether the vulnerability or risk influencing factors act before or after the main event (drop down), or both prior to and after the main event (drop down). Add value according to drop down list for the related category.

Identify vulnerability by selecting vulnerability factor.

1. Population
2. ChainEffects
3. Maintenance
4. GeographicScope
5. Time

Indicate whether the vulnerability or risk influencing factor (RIF) acts before or after (or both) the main event:

1. After
2. Before
3. B+A

"Before" is referring to additional threats to assets or barriers (as potential source of risk that can increase the frequency of main event or bring the top event to happen (the left side of the bow-tie; Figure 1)

"After" is referring to the consequences, to consequence categories "impacted" by the top events if found relevant (the right side of the bow-tie; Figure 1).

A complete list of values is presented in Annex A, Table 6.

4.7 Step 7 Assess probabilities

Assess probabilities (worst case) for each of the consequence dimensions.

Probabilities can be selected in the column left next to the consequences; marked Pr(CIE):

1. Very unlikely
2. Remote
3. Occasional
4. Probable
5. Frequent

There is an alternative way to input probabilities for Lifeline Quality and Lifeline Unavailability; namely by using the Quality impact and Delivery impact.

Quality impact

Duration: 0 - 6 hours

Involved persons: 10 000 - 100 000 per

Delivery impact

Duration: 1 - 7 days

Involved persons: 10 000 - 100 000 per

Figure 10: Quality and delivery impact

4.8 Step 8 Select consequences

Select the consequence class for the respective consequence dimension. The risk colour for each consequence dimension is then viewed, as it appears in the risk matrix.

Consequence dimension:

Life & health, Environment, Economy, Manageability, Political trust, Reputation, Lifeline quality and Lifeline unavailability

Each of the selected dimension should be valued like

1. Delimited
2. Some Damages
3. Serious
4. Critical
5. Catastrophic

A complete list of consequences is found in Table 5 in Annex A.

The colours are referring to the selected colours of the Risk matrix. The colours in the RiskMatrix can be changes or adapted to any local values, see Configuration.

4.9 Step 9 Describe causes

Describe Causes behind the event as basis for risk reduction measures (free text).

Describe causes behind the event (left side of screen).

Figure 11: Describe causes

4.10 Step 10 Risk reduction measures

Tick of the relevant Risk reduction measures taken from the RRMD by clicking the magnifying glass symbol. Choose expected "Risk reduction effect" from the drop-down list (Low, Medium, High) and observe "Risk w/RRM" on the screen.

Click the magnifying glass to open the RRMD (D4.3, 2019), see Figure 12.

Figure 12: Example of Risk reduction measures

Finally choose expected "Risk reduction effect" from the drop-down list (Low, Medium, High) and observe "Risk w/RRM" on the screen, see Figure 14.

After selecting the relevant measures, a copy of the selected ones are shown in the text box (lower left), see Figure 13.

Figure 13: Example of Risk reduction measures (text box)

Example of the text in the box:

FencesAndWalls(E=M);MotionDetectors(E=L);CameraSurveillance(E=L);BinaryContacts(E=L);SecureDoorsAndWindows(E=L);SecureLocks;DiscreetAppearance

The codes in the parentheses specify the risk reducing effect of the measure, e.g., (E=M) means medium effect.

Consequence	Risk	Risk w/RRM
Life and health		
Environment		
Economy	(2) Some dang	Medium risk
Manageability		
Political trust		
Reputation	(2) Some dang	Medium risk
Uptime quality	(3) Serious	Very low risk
Uptime avail.	(4) Critical	Medium risk

Figure 14: Example of Risk with reduction measures

4.11 Special conditions

The parameters in Figure 15 can be used if special conditions that temporarily increase the need for protection, exist.

Special conditions

- Gross Accident Potential
- Dependence between SCFs
- Internal/external communication issues
- This is a specific event (location)

Figure 15: Special conditions

4.12 Complete example

An example of a complete local event is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Example of a local defined event

4.14 Filter specification

Figure 19: Filter SQL command

Enter the WHERE clause of the SQL statement to filter out selected records. Note that the same syntax for filtering events also applies for the print event menu under the analysis menu. Some special functions/statements will be described below, and these are:

```
SCF(<SCF code 1>, [SCF code 2], [SCF code 3], ...)  
MainEvent(<Event code 1>, [Event code 2], [Event code 3], ... )  
TypeOfEvent = <EventType>  
TypeOfThreat = <ThreatType>
```

To use the **SCF()** function in the filter window you need to specify the SCF code. If multiple codes are specified, they are combined by the OR operator. See Table 7 for a list of all SCF codes available in InfraRisk-CP. For example, if you will list all risk elements in the database where a *control system* SCF for *Drinking water network* or *Drinking water tanks* has been specified, use the following filter:

```
SCF ("C122", "C131")
```

To get a wider scope, it is possible to search all risk elements related to e.g., *Drinking water tanks* by the following filter:

```
SCF ("C13")
```

since the code C13 represents *Drinking water tanks*. The code(s) should be enclosed with apostrophes.

The syntax for the **MainEvent()** function is similar to the **SCF()** function. A complete list of main events are shown in Table 8. As an example, to get a listing of natural events for seasonal flooding use the syntax:

```
MainEvent ("NM21")
```

To filter risk elements based on the type of event we may use the type of event syntax, for example:


```
EventType="Pollution"
```

Note that "Pollution" here is enclosed in apostrophes. In a similar way we may filter event by their type of threat, e.g.,

```
TypeOfThreat="Cyber"
```

It is possible to combine filtering statements, for example:

```
SCF("C152") AND TypeOfThreat="Cyber"
```

After a filtration is finished, you can use the "Filtered" MS-Access button (lower left corner) to remove the filter, or you can specify "True" in the filter window.

4.15 Reports

The available reports:

Figure 20: Available reports

4.15.1 Asset SCF ranking

Asset / SCF ranking. The assets / SCFs are linked according to their importance. The importance depends both on how many events they are linked to, how strong these links are, and the total risk for the corresponding events.

The SCF ranking is based on the result from the quantification of frequency and consequence of events. For each main event where a SCF is involved, the risk is calculated by multiplying the frequency with the sum of consequences. Then each SCF achieves a score which is the importance contribution times the risk. The importance contribution of an SCF with respect to a given event is shown as the "number" in Table 13, for example R90 gives an importance score of 90%. By summing over all main events for all SCFs it is possible to establish a ranking of SCFs. Note that the frequency and consequence values are given on a logarithmic scale, hence it is necessary to use the exponential function during the calculation in InfraRisk-CP.

Figure 22: Asset/SCF listing

4.15.3 Print events

First you have to specify a filter (SQL command); see chapter 4.14. You can leave this blank to list all the events.

Figure 23: Print events

4.16 Configurations

The configuration menu is shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Configuration menu

4.16.1 Edit risk matrix

The risk matrix may be calibrated see Figure 25. In the risk matrix you now click on a cell, and then you could change the colour/text of the cell as shown in Figure 26.

Figure 25: Edit the risk matrix

Figure 26: Edit one cell in the risk matrix

4.16.2 Edit quality matrix

Similarly to defining the colours and values for risk matrix, the consequence dimensions for lifeline quality can be calibrated from the configuration menu.

Click a cell in the matrix to edit the value/colour on the cell

	0 - 6 hours	6 - 24 hours	1 - 7 days	1 - 4 weeks	One to 6 months	More than 6 months
1 - 10 persons	Delimited	Delimited	Some Damages	Some Damages	Serious	Serious
10 - 100 persons	Delimited	Some Damages	Some Damages	Serious	Serious	Critical
100 - 1 000 persons	Some Damages	Some Damages	Serious	Serious	Critical	Critical
1 000 - 10 000 persons	Some Damages	Serious	Serious	Critical	Critical	Catastrophic
10 000 - 100 000 persons	Serious	Serious	Critical	Critical	Catastrophic	Catastrophic
More than 100 000 persons	Serious	Critical	Critical	Catastrophic	Catastrophic	Catastrophic

Figure 27: Edit quality matrix

4.16.3 Edit delivery matrix

Similarly, to defining the colours and values for risk matrix, the consequence dimensions for lifeline unavailability (quantity) can be calibrated from the configuration menu.

Analysis of main events: x Define matrix colours and values x

Click a cell in the matrix to edit the value/colour on the cell

	0 - 6 hours	6 - 24 hours	1 - 7 days	1 - 4 weeks	One to 6 months	More than 6 months
1 - 10 persons	Delimited	Delimited	Some Damages	Some Damages	Serious	Serious
10 - 100 persons	Delimited	Some Damages	Some Damages	Serious	Serious	Critical
100 - 1 000 persons	Some Damages	Some Damages	Serious	Serious	Critical	Critical
1 000 - 10 000 persons	Some Damages	Serious	Serious	Critical	Critical	Catastrophic
10 000 - 100 000 persons	Serious	Serious	Critical	Critical	Catastrophic	Catastrophic
More than 100 000 persons	Serious	Critical	Critical	Catastrophic	Catastrophic	Catastrophic

Figure 28: Edit delivery matrix

4.16.4 Attack ranges

Attack ranges from the configuration menu is used to specify the following quantities:

- fL = Lowest attack frequency (default = one per hundred years)
- fH = Highest attack frequency (default = 10 per year)
- pL = Lowest attack success probability (default = one out of hundred)
- pH = Highest attack success probability (default = one out of two)

The frequencies should reflect the best and worst case respectively. With the best case we mean a situation where all risk factors (scores) take the values considered to give the lowest frequency of attacks, and where the worst case means that all factors take the values considered to give the highest frequency of attacks. Similarly, for the probabilities. Default values are given. These values are used when actual frequencies and probabilities are calculated based on scores.

Analysis of main events × **Attack ranges** ×

Lowest attack frequency	<input type="text" value="0.01"/>
Highest attack frequency	<input type="text" value="10"/>
Lowest attack success probability	<input type="text" value="0.01"/>
Highest attack success probability	<input type="text" value="0.5"/>

Figure 29: Attack ranges

5 Frequency assessment of physical and cyber attacks

5.1 Frequency of physical attack

For physical attacks the following questions with possible answers are provided for the frequency of an attack:

Q1: How attractive is the asset to the perpetrator?

- 1=Very low attractiveness
- 2=Low attractiveness
- 3=Medium attractiveness
- 4=High attractiveness
- 5=Very high attractiveness

The attractiveness is influenced by the possible damage potential, the political, social and economic importance, the psychological effects as well as by the affected end-users (military institutions, parliaments, chemical industry, residence of important people like a president or similar). The classification of the attractiveness is done subjectively as for example the perpetrator is not known at the time the assessment is done.

Q2: How is the actual security situation evaluated by the security authorities?

- 1=Police intelligence does not expect any threats
- 3=Evidences for a threat exist
- 4=The asset is endangered, an attack cannot be excluded
- 5=The asset is in significant danger, an attack should be expected

Information about the actual security situation can usually be gained at the responsible police authority.

Q3: How relevant is the asset for the overall water supply?

- 1=Low
- 2=Medium
- 3=High
- 4=Very high
- 5=Critical

A systematic can be applied to answer this question. For example, each answer can be matched to a certain percentage of end-users/people (e.g. Low -> <10 %, Medium -> <25 %, ...). Other possibilities could be the matching of answers with percentages of the overall drinking water amount affected or similar. It might often be true that the asset is e.g. very relevant for a certain part of the network but only medium relevant for the overall network. In these cases, the relevance of the asset should be rated with regard to its importance for the affected part of the network.

Q4: How difficult is it to carry out a criminal act?

- 1=Extremely high effort necessary (1 point)
- 2=Medium effort necessary (2 points)
- 3=Little to no effort necessary (3 points)

The choice of an answer is based on the assumed effort of the perpetrator and the possibility to be successful with that assumed effort. For the evaluation the attack path of “lowest resistance” should be considered.

Q5: Do special environmental conditions exist that temporarily increase the need for protection?

- 1=No special conditions (1 point)
- 2=Few special conditions (2 points)
- 3=Substantial special conditions (3 points)

Here special temporarily occurring events or conditions are regarded. Examples could be government visits, major events, festivals, etc.

Now let L_1 be the sum of scores achieved for questions Q1 to Q5. L_1 can take values in the range 5 to 21, and a standardized score between 0 and 1 is given by: $L = (L_1 - 5) / (21 - 5) = (L_1 - 5) / 16$. The frequency of a physical attack is now calculated as:

$$f = f_L \left(\frac{f_H}{f_L} \right)^L \quad (1)$$

Where f_L and f_H are defined as limiting values for the frequency.

5.2 Probability of physical attack succeeding

The following questions with possible answers are provided for the probability of a successful attack:

Q6: How is the asset built? Is it easily visible for the public?

- 3=Object not visible for public
- 2=Object visible without restrictions
- 1=Object only accessible by interruptions of the public life (railway, streets, ...)

For example, if an asset is built in a very enlivened area of a city an attack is more likely to be detected by people and thus, not succeeding compared to an attack on an asset that is built in a forest where a perpetrator is more or less undisturbed.

Q7: In which resistance class is the perimeter protection built?

- 2=RC1-RC2
- 1=RC3-RC4
- 0=RC5-RC6

The different resistance classes used in the possible answers are defined in DIN EN 1627. (DIN 2011). If there is any gap or similar in the perimeter protection, the score of 2 is given.

Q8: In which resistance classes are the walls of the buildings including their integrated integrations?

- 2=RC1-RC2
- 1=RC3-RC4
- 0=RC5-RC6

The different resistance classes used in the possible answers are defined in DIN EN 1627. (DIN 2011)

If there is any gap or similar in the protection like unprotected windows lower than the first floor, the score of 2 is given.

Q9: *How is the sensory surveillance realized?*

- 2=No sensory surveillance
- 1=Binary Contacts, e.g. open/closed
- 0=Measured value-based surveillance, e.g. sensitivity of sensor can be regulated

The evaluation of the sensory surveillance should be realized at the weakest position of the barriers.

Q10: *How are organizational measures implemented?*

- 2=No organizational measures exist
- 1=Primary dissuasive measures are implemented like alarms, only irregular patrolling
- 0=Organizational measures ensure, that a direct defensive reaction is initiated (e.g. the police is called, the system is shut down, ...)

Now let Q_1 denote the sum of scores for questions Q6-Q10. Q_1 can take values in the range 1 to 11, and a standardized score between 0 and 1 is given by: $Q = (Q_1 - 1) / (11 - 1)$. The probability of success of an attempt is given by:

$$p = p_L \left(\frac{p_H}{p_L} \right)^Q \quad (2)$$

Where p_L and p_H are defined as limiting values for the probability.

5.3 Frequency of successful physical attack

The frequency of a successful attack is given by

$$f_A = f \times p \quad (3)$$

The frequency in equation (3) gives directly a frequency per year. In some situation it is desirable to assign the frequency of successful attack to a likelihood *category*. In InfraRisk CP the following likelihood categories are defined:

1. Very unlikely Less than once per 100 year
2. Remote Once per 10-100 year

- | | |
|---------------|------------------------|
| 3. Occasional | Once per 1-10 year |
| 4. Probable | 1 to 12 times a year |
| 5. Frequent | More than once a month |

These categories are used to transform the frequency in equation (3) to a category number.

5.4 Frequency of cyber attack

For assessing frequencies of cyber attacks a list of questions is provided, where scores are obtained for each sub question (s_1, s_2 etc). The scores marked by a star (*) are common to all component conditions considered as global conditions for the critical infrastructure under consideration. Scores not marked with a star are considered as component specific conditions. If no information is available a score of 3 is given. If a question is not considered relevant, the score excluded from the aggregation. The scores are grouped under some headlines:

How attractive it is to make an attempt to attack the water distribution system..?

- s_1 = ..in terms of Recognisability (1=very low,2=low,3=medium,4=high,5=very high) *
- s_2 = .. in terms of Symbolism (1=very low,2=low,3=medium,4=high,5=very high) *
- s_3 = .. in terms of Potential for economic profit (ransom) (1=very low,2=low,3=medium,4=high,5=very high) *
- s_4 = in terms of Potential for political profit (1=very low,2=low,3=medium,4=high,5=very high) *

Note: *Recognisability* deals with attackers having a desired to be recognized within a community. Typically, this could be individual hackers. *Symbolism* could be relevant for terrorist groups which often have an objective to cause fear and uncertainty. *Economic profit* would relate to organized crime. *Political issues* could relate to foreign nations or political groups within one nation.

Organizational issues

- s_5 = Measures implemented towards insiders (1=very high,2=high,3=medium,4=low,5=very low) *
- s_6 = Quality of internal surveillance and intelligence systems (1=very high,2=high, 3=medium, 4=low,5=very low) *
- s_7 = Systematic preparedness exercises, investigation and learning (1=very high,2=high,3=medium, 4=low,5=very low) *
- s_8 = Security focus in agreements with vendors and contractors (1=very high,2=high,3=medium, 4=low,5=very low) *

Conditions affecting if an attacker will make an attack attempt for a specific component

- s_9 = How vulnerable the component seems from the attacker's point of view (1=very low, 2=low, 3=medium,4=high,5=very high)
- s_{10} = Visible protective measures by the utility manager for the specific component (1=high, 5=low)
- s_{11} = How critical the component seems from the attacker's point of view (1=very low,2=low, 3=medium,4=high,5=very high)

- s_{12} = Accessibility of the particular component (1=very low,2=low,3=medium,4=high,5=very high)
- s_{13} = Attacker’s capability vs required capability to make an attempt (1=very low,2=low,3=medium, 4=high,5=very high) *
- s_{14} = Attacker’s available resources vs required resources to make an attempt (1=very low,2=low, 3=medium,4=high,5=very high) *

Evidence with respect to possible attacks:

- s_{15} = How is the actual cyber security situation evaluated by the security authorities (police, intelligence etc., 1=very low,2=low, 3=medium, 4=high,5=very high) *
- s_{16} = Evidence from internal surveillance (computerized monitoring tools). This quantity is measured in terms of number of attack attempts per time unit, typically per year.

To combine the scores into a frequency of attack the following arguments are made:

- The scores $s_1 - s_4$ could be seen as competing scores, and we let $S_A = \max (s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4) + \Delta_A$ be a total attractiveness score. Here¹ $\Delta_A = 0.25 \ln n$, where n counts the number of scores equal the maximum score. $\Delta_A = 0$ if the maximum score is 1 or 5. Thus Δ_A accounts for very many scores equal to the maximum score.
- For the organizational factors affecting the frequency of attack we calculate an average score: $S_O = (s_5 + s_6 + s_7 + s_9)/4$
- For the conditions influencing willingness of an attacker to make an attempt an average score is also proposed: $S_W = (s_9 + s_{10} + s_{11} + s_{12} + s_{13} + s_{14})/6$
- To obtain a total normalized score for the likelihood of an attack, we take the average of S_A, S_O, S_W and s_{15} (national evidence) and standardize between 0 and 1: $L = (S_A + S_O + S_W + s_{15} - 4) / (20-4)$.

The frequency of an attack based on the influencing conditions is given by:

$$f_S = f_L \left(\frac{f_H}{f_L} \right)^L \tag{4}$$

The yearly frequency f_S based on the assessment of conditions should be compared to the observed frequency, s_{16} . A natural approach to obtain a combined yearly frequency measure is to calculate a weighted average of f_S and s_{16} . With equal weights this yields:

$$f = (f_S + s_{16})/2 \tag{5}$$

Note that f_S would normally be updated rather seldom, for example every 5 years. On the other side, s_{16} would in principle be available in real-time. This is crucial for real-time update of the risk profile.

¹ The argument for the adjustment is as follows. Assume that for each of the questions, the frequency of attack is given on the form $f = a \cdot b^S$, where a and b are constants, and S is the score. Given that n questions get the highest score, say S , then the total frequency is $f_{\text{Tot}} = n \cdot a \cdot b^S$. To “account” for multiple answers getting the highest score, we seek an adjusted score: $S+\Delta$. Δ is then determined by: $f_{\text{Tot}} = a \cdot b^{S+\Delta} = n \cdot a \cdot b^S$. This gives $\Delta = (1/b) \ln n$. Here $\ln n$ is the natural logarithm of n . Note that b is a factor determining the increase in the frequency when the score increases with a nominal value of 1. Typical values for b would be in the interval 3 to 10, and we pragmatically choose $b = 4$.

5.5 Probability of cyber attack succeeding

For the probability assessment of a successful attack another set of questions are provided:

Likelihood of succeeding in an attempt

- s_{17} = Attacker’s capability vs required capability to succeed in an attempt (1=very low,2=low, 3=medium,4=high,5=very high) *
- s_{18} = Attacker’s available resources vs required resources to succeed in an attempt (1=very low,2=low, 3=medium,4=high,5=very high) *
- s_{19} = Explicit protective measures (1=very high,2=high,3=medium,4=low,5=very low) *

Comments: For explicit protective measures one should take into account (i) use of encryption, (ii) regular updates of software (safety patches), (iii) avoiding possibility to send control commands “from home” to the control systems of the water distribution system (iv) proper governance of emerging technologies like IoT when integrated into the control systems and (v) well design software architecture.

To obtain a probability measure for success of the attack, we first calculate a standardised score $Q = (s_{17} + s_{18} + s_{19} + s_6 + s_7 - 5)/20$, where Q is in the interval from 0 to 1.

Note that in this score we have included two of the organizational conditions which also were “counted” in the likelihood assessment. It could be argued that this will give “double counting”, but since we always “normalize”, this is considered not to be a big problem. The probability of a successful attack is given by:

$$p = p_L \left(\frac{p_H}{p_L} \right)^Q \tag{6}$$

5.6 Frequency of successful cyber attack

The frequency of a successful attack is given by:

$$f_A = f \times p \tag{7}$$

The frequency in equation (7) gives directly a frequency per year. In some situation it is desirable to assign the frequency of successful attack to a likelihood *category*. In InfraRisk the following likelihood categories are defined:

1. Very unlikely Less than once per 100 year
2. Remote Once per 10-100 year
3. Occasional Once per 1-10 year
4. Probable 1 to 12 times a year
5. Frequent More than once a month

These categories are used to transform the frequency in equation (7) to a category number.

6 References

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ANNEX A: Additional information

Table 2: List of Main events [from RIDB](#)

Event ID	Scenario Description	Event code	Cyber/Physical
1	External attacker generates a physical caused pollution of groundwater affecting raw water bodies; which might lead to a quality issue	MC21	P
2	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of transmission devices affecting catchment area; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
3	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of transmission devices affecting catchment area; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
4	Natural phenomena generates a physical caused pollution of groundwater affecting raw water bodies; which might lead to a quality issue		P
5	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of sensors affecting catchment area; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
6	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of transmission devices affecting catchment area; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
7	External attacker generates a physical caused destruction of well affecting catchment area; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC21	P
8	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of sensors affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
9	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of sensors affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	B
10	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of transmission devices affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	B
11	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of transmission devices affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
12	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of dosing system affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	B
13	Natural phenomena generates a physical caused pollution of water under treatment affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue		P
14	Natural phenomena generates a physical caused destruction of additives affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue		P
15	Human fault generates a physical caused pollution of water under treatment affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue	TF12	P
16	External attacker generates a physical caused pollution of additives affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue	MC21	P
17	Human fault generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	TF13	B

Event ID	Scenario Description	Event code	Cyber/Physical
18	Human fault generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	TF13	B
19	External attacker generates a physical caused destruction of pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC21	P
20	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of sensors affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
21	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of sensors affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
22	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of transmission devices affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
23	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of transmission devices affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
24	Human fault generates a physical caused manipulation of drinking water pipes affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	TF13	P
25	External attacker generates a physical caused pollution of drinking water taps affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	MC21	P
26	External attacker generates a physical caused pollution of fire hydrants affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	P
27	External attacker generates a physical caused destruction of drinking water pipes affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC21	P
28	External attacker generates a physical caused pollution of drinking water tanks; which might lead to a quality issue	MC21	P
29	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of sensors affecting drinking water tanks; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
30	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of transmission devices affecting drinking water tanks; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
31	External attacker generates a physical caused destruction of drinking water tanks; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC21	P
32	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
33	Interdependent CI generates a physical caused interruption of power transformer affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quantity issue	TF	P
34	Interdependent CI generates a physical caused interruption of power transformer affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	TF	P
35	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of transmission devices affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
36	External attacker generates a physical caused destruction of power transformer affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC21	P

Event ID	Scenario Description	Event code	Cyber/Physical
37	External attacker generates a physical caused destruction of power transformer affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC21	P
38	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of sensors affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
39	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of sensors affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	B
40	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
41	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of sensors affecting catchment area; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
42	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of transmission devices affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
43	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting catchment area; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
44	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	B
45	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting wastewater treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	B
46	Human fault generates a physical caused manipulation of valve affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	TF13	P
47	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of control center affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
48	Human fault generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of control center affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	TF13	B
49	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	B
50	External attacker generates a cyber caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a financial issue	MC24	C
51	Internal attacker generates a cyber caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a financial issue	MC24	C
52	External attacker generates a cyber caused manipulation of transferred information affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	C
53	External attacker generates a cyber caused manipulation of transferred information affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	C
54	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of control system affecting pressure boosting station; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
55	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused destruction of control system affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	B

Event ID	Scenario Description	Event code	Cyber/Physical
56	External attacker generates a physical caused destruction of dosing system affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	MC21	P
57	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting drinking water tanks; which might lead to a reputation issue	MC24	B
58	Human fault generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting drinking water tanks; which might lead to a reputation issue	TF13	B
59	External supplier generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	TF13	B
60	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of sensors affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a reputation issue	MC24	B
61	External attacker generates a physical caused pollution of drinking water pipes affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	MC21	P
62	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of sensors affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	B
63	Interdependent CI generates a physical caused pollution of surface water affecting raw water bodies; which might lead to a issue	TF	P
64	External attacker generates a physical caused manipulation of valve affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	P
65	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting raw water bodies; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
66	External attacker generates a physical caused manipulation of pump affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC21	P
67	External attacker generates a physical caused manipulation of valve affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC21	P
68	External attacker generates a physical caused manipulation of drinking water pipes affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC21	P
69	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
70	External attacker generates a cyber caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a quality issue	MC24	C
71	External attacker generates a cyber caused manipulation of transferred information affecting drinking water network; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	C
72	External attacker generates a cyber caused manipulation of media channels; which might lead to a reputation issue	MC24	C
73	External attacker generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of control system affecting drinking water tanks; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	B
74	External attacker generates a cyber caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a quantity issue	MC24	C

Event ID	Scenario Description	Event code	Cyber/Physical
75	External attacker generates a cyber caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a reputation issue	MC24	C
76	Human fault generates a cyber caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a reputation issue	TF1	C
77	Human fault generates a cyber caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a quantity issue	TF1	C
78	Human fault generates a cyber caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a quality issue	TF1	C
79	Human fault generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a quantity issue	TF1	B
80	Human fault generates a cyber-physical caused manipulation of server; which might lead to a quality issue	TF1	B
81	Interdependent CI generates a physical caused pollution of water under treatment affecting water treatment plant; which might lead to a quality issue	TF	P

Table 3: Levels of Main events

Level	Code	Description
Level1	M	(Malicious) acts against nation, inhabitants, or interest (M)
	N	Natural event (N)
	T	Technical catastrophe (T)
Level2	MC	Crime (C)
	NM	Meteorological (M)
	TF	Technical/ human failure in infrastructure (F)
Level3	MC2	Sabotage (2)
	TF1	Water supply (1)
Level4	MC21	Attack against installations (1)
	MC24	Data hacking (4)
	TF12	Waterworks and purification (2)
	TF13	Pipelines (3)

Table 4: Values to define if the event is cyber or physical

	Code	Description
isCyber	B	Cyber/physical
	C	Cyber
	P	Physical

Table 5: Consequence classes for each consequence dimension

Consequence dimension	Class	Description
Life & health	(1) Delimited	Up to 5 fatalities, Up to 20 injured
	(2) Some damage	Up to 50 fatalities, Up to 200 injured
	(3) Serious	Up to 300 fatalities, Up to 1200 injured
	(4) Critical	Up to 1000 fatalities, Up to 4000 injured
	(5) Catastrophic	More than 1000 fatalities, More than 4000 injured
Environment	(1) Delimited	Minor environmental changes
	(2) Some damage	Major environmental changes
	(3) Serious	Moderate environmental injurious to health changes
	(4) Critical	Store environmental injurious to health changes
	(5) Catastrophic	Destruction of human habitat
Economy	(1) Delimited	Up to 0.01 % of GNP
	(2) Some damage	Up to 0.1 % of GNP
	(3) Serious	Up to 1 % of GNP
	(4) Critical	Up to 10 % of GNP
	(5) Catastrophic	More than 10 % of GNP
Manageability	(1) Delimited	No or minor disturbances
	(2) Some damage	Short disturbances
	(3) Serious	Major disturbances
	(4) Critical	Serious disturbances
	(5) Catastrophic	Critical disturbances, permanent changes
Political trust	(1) Delimited	No significant effects
	(2) Some damage	Passively constructive, loyalty, adoption
	(3) Serious	Actively constructive, disturbances, protest, demanding changes
	(4) Critical	Passively destructive, non-participation, substitutional behavior
	(5) Catastrophic	Actively destructive, political exit, violence, system delegitimizing, system change
Lifeline quality	(1) Delimited	
	(2) Some damage	
	(3) Serious	
	(4) Critical	
	(5) Catastrophic	
Lifeline unavailability	(1) Delimited	
	(2) Some damage	
	(3) Serious	
	(4) Critical	
	(5) Catastrophic	

Table 6: Values of vulnerability factors

VulnerabilityFactor	Influence	Comment
Area	(1) Minor	Open ground
	(2) Small	Transportation trace
	(3) Medium	Street in town, dens building mass, landslide risk area etc
	(4) Huge	Close to dangerous installation, factors etc
	(5) Very huge	Terminal for person traffic or tunnel
Geographic scope	(1) Local	+ neighbourhood in large city or equivalent
	(2) City	+ Large city, major suburbia
	(3) Region	Limited to regions
	(4) National	+ Capital
	(5) International	If current country is affected
Population density pr 1 km²	(1) 1 - 4	Isolated village settlement
	(2) 5 - 29	Village settlement
	(3) 30 - 199	Open settlement
	(4) 200 - 499	Suburbia
	(5) 500 - 15200	Cities
Outdoor temperature	(1) +20 °C - +30 °C	No heating or cooling demand
	(2) +5 °C - + 20 °C	Some heating demand
	(3) -5 °C - +5 °C, > +30 °C	Significant heating or cooling demand
	(4) -20 °C - -5 °C	Large heating demand
	(5) < -20 °C	Heating critical for survival
Time of day	(1) Night	Silence
	(2) Evening	Most people are at home
	(3) Working hours	Most people are at work
	(4) Early morning	Early morning
	(5) Rush hours	From and to work, school etc
Duration	(1) < 1 day	Fast normalization
	(2) < 1 week	Normalization within weeks
	(3) > 1 month	Normalization takes more than one months
	(4) > 6 months	Normalization takes up to one year
	(5) Quasi permanent	Years or decades to normalize
Dependency with other societal critical functions	(1) Very little	Small dependencies
	(2) Little	Medium asymmetric dependencies
	(3) Medium	Medium symmetric dependencies
	(4) Huge	Strong Medium symmetric dependencies
	(5) Very huge	Strong symmetric dependencies

VulnerabilityFactor	Influence	Comment
Substitution opportunities for infrastructure	(1) Very huge	Easy substitution
	(4) Huge	Substitution with some problems
	(3) Medium	Substitution requires significant effort
	(4) Little	Substitution difficult
	(5) Very little	Indispensability
Degree of coupling	(1) Very little	Anarchism
	(2) Little	Simple set of rules sufficient for activity functions
	(3) Medium	Complex set of rules sufficient for activity functions
	(4) Huge	Operative governing functions necessary
	(5) Very huge	Strong centralized governed with small tolerance for deviations
Culture	(1) Very favourable	Frankness, humility, real competence, honesty
	(2) Favourable	Cooperation climate, looks for opportunities, consciousness
	(3) Medium	Caution, delays, naivety
	(4) Unfavourable	Reluctance, anxiety, isolation
	(5) Very unfavourable	Power struggle, closed, dishonesty
Mental preparedness	(1) Very favourable	Frequent targeted training
	(2) Favourable	Significant effective measures
	(3) Medium	Good risk consciousness, some measures
	(4) Unfavourable	Under communicated risk
	(5) Very unfavourable	Lack of potential risk consciousness
Chain effects	(1) Very favourable	
	(2) Favourable	
	(3) Medium	
	(4) Unfavourable	
	(5) Very unfavourable	
Quality of operational procedure and knowledge	(1) Very favourable	Organizations are very well trained for operation of associated infrastructures
	(2) Favourable	Organizations are well trained for operation of associated infrastructures
	(3) Medium	Organizations are trained for operation of associated infrastructures
	(4) Unfavourable	Organizations have little experience with operation of associated infrastructures
	(5) Very unfavourable	Organizations are unfamiliar with operation of associated infrastructures

VulnerabilityFactor	Influence	Comment
Level of maintenance and renewal	(1) Very favourable	Good planning and execution of maintenance and renewal
	(2) Favourable	Some planning and execution of maintenance and renewal. Resources could be challenge
	(3) Medium	Some planning of maintenance and renewal. Short of resources
	(4) Unfavourable	Little planning of maintenance and renewal. Very limited resources for maint. and renewal. Ageing problems
	(5) Very unfavourable	Organization characterized by break down maintenance. Significant aging problem

Table 7: Complete list of SCFs / Assets with corresponding codes

SCF / Asset hierarchy		Codes (column 1-4)					
Critical infrastructure, basic (B)	Electrical power (1)	Production plants (1)	Class 1	B	B1	B11	B111
			Class 2	B	B1	B11	B112
			Class 3	B	B1	B11	B113
			Class 4	B	B1	B11	B114
		Transformer and transformer cubicle front (2)	Class 1	B	B1	B12	B121
			Class 2	B	B1	B12	B122
			Class 3	B	B1	B12	B123
		Distribution net (3)	Class 1	B	B1	B13	B131
			Class 2	B	B1	B13	B132
			Class 3	B	B1	B13	B133
		Dams, barrages (4)		B	B1	B14	
			Control centres and SCADA-systems (5)		B	B1	B15
	Mobile backup systems (6)			B	B1	B16	
	Electronic communication (2)	Phone and cable systems (1)	National centrals	B	B2	B21	B211
			Nodes	B	B2	B21	B212
			Important switchboards and other important user applications	B	B2	B21	B213
		Mobile phones (2)	National centrals	B	B2	B22	B221
			Nodes	B	B2	B22	B222
Base stations			B	B2	B22	B223	

SCF / Asset hierarchy			Codes (column 1-4)						
		Internet (3)	NIX'es etc	B	B2	B23	B231		
			Internet Service Providers	B	B2	B23	B232		
		Closed communication systems for the authorities (4)	Digital net of army	B	B2	B24	B241		
			Rescue net	B	B2	B24	B242		
		Radio communication (5)	Aviation control central	B	B2	B25	B251		
			Costal radio	B	B2	B25	B252		
			Broadcasting	B	B2	B25	B253		
		Satellite based infrastructures, earth based stations (6)	For meteorology, communication, Broadcasting, Navigation, Environment monitoring	B	B2	B26	B26		
		Mobile backup systems (7)		B	B2	B27			
		Critical infrastructure, remaining (C)	Water and sewage systems (1)	Catchment area	Control center	C	C1	C11	C111
					Sensor	C	C1	C11	C112
					Transmission devices	C	C1	C11	C113
					Well	C	C1	C11	C114
Drinking water network	Control center			C	C1	C12	C121		
	Control system			C	C1	C12	C122		
	Dosing system			C	C1	C12	C123		
	Drinking water pipes			C	C1	C12	C124		
	Drinking water taps			C	C1	C12	C125		
	Fire hydrants			C	C1	C12	C126		
	Pump			C	C1	C12	C127		
	Sensor			C	C1	C12	C128		
	Spring water			C	C1	C12	C129		
	Transferred information		C	C1	C12	C12A			
	Tunnel		C	C1	C12	C12B			
	Valve		C	C1	C12	C12C			
Buildings	C		C1	C12	C12D				
Drinking water tanks	Control system		C	C1	C13	C131			
	Drinking water tanks		C	C1	C13	C132			
	Pump		C	C1	C13	C133			
	Sensor		C	C1	C13	C134			

SCF / Asset hierarchy			Codes (column 1-4)					
			Transmission devices	C	C1	C13	C135	
			Valve	C	C1	C13	C136	
			Buildings	C	C1	C13	C137	
		Pressure boosting station	Control system	C	C1	C14	C141	
			Power transformer	C	C1	C14	C142	
			Pressure boosting station	C	C1	C14	C143	
			Sensor	C	C1	C14	C144	
			Transferred information	C	C1	C14	C145	
			Transmission devices	C	C1	C14	C146	
			Buildings	C	C1	C14	C147	
		Raw water bodies	Control system	C	C1	C15	C151	
			Groundwater	C	C1	C15	C152	
			Surface water	C	C1	C15	C153	
		Wastewater treatment plant	Control system	C	C1	C16	C161	
			Power transformer	C	C1	C16	C162	
			Buildings	C	C1	C16	C163	
		Water treatment plant	Additives	C	C1	C18	C181	
			Control system	C	C1	C18	C182	
			Dosing system	C	C1	C18	C183	
			Power transformer	C	C1	C18	C184	
			Pump	C	C1	C18	C185	
			Sensor	C	C1	C18	C186	
			Transmission devices	C	C1	C18	C187	
			Valve	C	C1	C18	C188	
			Water under treatment	C	C1	C18	C189	
			Buildings	C	C1	C18	C18A	
		Other	Media channels	C	C1	C19	C191	
			Server	C	C1	C19	C192	
		Oil- and gas supply (2)	Offshore installations (1)		C	C2	C21	
			Pipelines (2)		C	C2	C22	
			Land terminals and refineries (3)		C	C2	C23	
			Depots (4)		C	C2	C24	
			Control centres and SCADA-systems (5)		C	C2	C25	
		Transport (3)	Aviation (1)	Traffic control (1)	C	C3	C31	C31
				Plane/helicopter (2)	C	C3	C31	C32

SCF / Asset hierarchy			Codes (column 1-4)				
	Railway (2)	Airport (3)	C	C3	C31	C33	
		Train controll (1)	C	C3	C32	C321	
		Station (2)	C	C3	C32	C322	
		Freight terminal (3)	C	C3	C32	C323	
		Tunnel (4)	C	C3	C32	C324	
		Railway bridge (5)	C	C3	C32	C325	
		Remaining track (6)	C	C3	C32	C326	
	Train (7)	C	C3	C32	C327		
	Metro/Tram (3)	Train controll (1)	C	C3	C33	C331	
		Station (2)	C	C3	C33	C332	
		Tunnel (3)	C	C3	C33	C333	
		Bridge (4)	C	C3	C33	C334	
		Remaining track (5)	C	C3	C33	C335	
		Train/Tram (6)	C	C3	C33	C336	
	Road transportation (4)	Traffic control (1)	C	C3	C34	C341	
		Tunnel (2)	C	C3	C34	C342	
		Bridge (3)	C	C3	C34	C343	
		Open road (4)	C	C3	C34	C344	
		Domestic ferry (5)	C	C3	C34	C345	
	Maritime (5)	Sea terminals, harbours (1)	C	C3	C35	C351	
		Passenger ship (2)	C	C3	C35	C352	
		Cargo ship (3)	C	C3	C35	C353	
		Oil/gas tanker (4)	C	C3	C35	C354	
	Bank and finance (4)	National clearing systems (1)	C	C4	C41		
		Payments system (2)	C	C4	C42		
		Securities systems(3)	C	C4	C43		
	Other critical infrastructure (O)	Food support(1)	Logistics system (1)	O	O1	O11	
			Hygiene and safety (2)	O	O1	O12	
		Sanitation (2)	Waste transportation (1)	O	O2	O21	
			Waste depot (2)	O	O2	O22	
		Health, social and social security services (3)	Specialist health services hospitals (1)	O	O3	O31	
			Primary health services (2)	O	O3	O32	
Police, emergency- and		Social services (3)	O	O3	O33		
		Support of medicines (4)	O	O3	O34		
		Laboratories (5)	O	O3	O35		

SCF / Asset hierarchy			Codes (column 1-4)				
	rescue services (4)	Systems for social security services		O	03	036	
		Police registers (1)		O	04	041	
		Police stations (2)		O	04	042	
		Emergency and rescue services (3)		O	04	043	
		Fire brigade (4)		O	04	044	
	Public management (5)	Parliament (1)		O	05	051	
		Government and administration, crisis management (2)		O	05	052	
		The judiciary (3)		O	05	053	
		Head of defence (4)		O	05	054	
	Media and news communication (6)	Radio- and television companies (1)		O	06	061	
		Press, hard copies(2)		O	06	062	
		Internet papers (3)		O	06	063	
		Public information services (4)		O	06	064	
	Important industries (7)	Chemical plants and depots (1)		O	07	071	
		Nuclear reactors and nuclear depots (2)		O	07	072	
		Defence industry (3)		O	07	073	
		Control centres and SCADA-systems (4)		O	07	074	
	National symbols (8)	Buildings cultural institutions and monuments (1)		O	08	081	
		Mobile objects (2)		O	08	082	
		Institutional evecton (3)		O	08	083	
Institutional persons (4)			O	08	084		

Table 8: Complete list of main events with corresponding codes

Event Hierachy				Codes (column 1-4)			
Natural event (N)	Meteorological (M)	Strong wind (1)	Storm, hurricane (1)	N	NM	NM1	NM11
			Whirlwind, tornado (2)	N	NM	NM1	NM12

Event Hierachy				Codes (column 1-4)			
		Flooding (2)	Seasonal flooding (1)	N	NM	NM2	NM21
			Storm flooding (2)	N	NM	NM2	NM22
			Spring flooding (3)	N	NM	NM2	NM23
		Extreme precipitation (3)	Rain (1)	N	NM	NM3	NM31
			Snow (2)	N	NM	NM3	NM32
			Drought (3)	N	NM	NM3	NM33
		Extreme temperature (4)	High temperature (1)	N	NM	NM4	NM41
			Low temperature (2)	N	NM	NM4	NM42
		Stroke of lightning (5)	Lightening (1)	N	NM	NM5	NM51
	Geological/Geotechnical (G)	Snow slide (1)	Snow slide over infrastructure (1)	N	NG	NG1	NG11
			Snow slide over buildings (2)	N	NG	NG1	NG12
		Landslide (2)	Land slide over infrastructure (1)	N	NG	NG2	NG21
			Land slide over buildings (2)	N	NG	NG2	NG22
			Land slide into water (3)	N	NG	NG2	NG23
		Earthquake (3)	Less than 5 Richter (1)	N	NG	NG3	NG31
			5 Richter or more (2)	N	NG	NG3	NG32
		Tsunami (4)	National impact (1)	N	NG	NG4	NG41
			Regional impact (2)	N	NG	NG4	NG42
		Volcanism (5)	Not in use (1)	N	NG	NG5	NG51
			National downfall fallout(2)	N	NG	NG5	NG52
		Calderac explosion (6)	Not in use(1)	N	NG	NG6	NG61
			Global impact, national downfall fallout (2)	N	NG	NG6	NG62
	Hit by cosmic objects (C)	Meteorite (asteroid) (1)	National impact (1)	N	NC	NC1	NC11
			Regional impact (2)	N	NC	NC1	NC12

Event Hierachy				Codes (column 1-4)			
			Global impact (3)	N	NC	NC1	NC13
		Comet (2)	Urban impact (1)	N	NC	NC2	NC21
			National impact (2)	N	NC	NC2	NC22
Medical / biological catastrophe (B)	Plants and animals (P)	Transferable disease (1)	Zoonotic (between humans and animals) (1)	B	BP	BP1	BP11
			Non-zoonotic (2)	B	BP	BP1	BP12
	Humans (H)	Pandemic (1)	Flu (1)	B	BH	BH1	BH11
			SARS (2)	B	BH	BH1	BH12
			Not in use (3)	B	BH	BH1	BH13
		Non pandemic (2)	Other diseases (1)	B	BH	BH2	BH21
Technical event (T)	Release of dangerous substances (D)	Chemical (1)		T	TD	TD1	
		Biological (2)		T	TD	TD2	
		Radiological (3)		T	TD	TD3	
		Other (4)		T	TD	TD4	
	Accident (A)	Fire, industrial (1)		T	TA	TA1	
		Explosion, Industrial (2)		T	TA	TA2	
		Transportation accident (3)		T	TA	TA3	
		Structural collapse (4)		T	TA	TA4	
		ICT system failure (5)		T	TA	TA5	
		Other (6)		T	TA	TA6	
	Technical/ human failure in infrastructure (F)	Water supply (1)	Water source (1)	T	TF	TF1	TF11
			Waterworks and purification (2)	T	TF	TF1	TF12
			Pipelines (3)	T	TF	TF1	TF13
		Safe food (2)		T	TF	TF2	
		Sewage and refuse collection (3)	Sewer (1)	T	TF	TF3	TF31
			Surface Water (2)	T	TF	TF3	TF32
			Refuse collection (3)	T	TF	TF3	TF33

Event Hierachy				Codes (column 1-4)			
		Transportation services (4)		T	TF	TF4	
		Financial services (5)		T	TF	TF5	
		Energy supply (6)		T	TF	TF6	
		Communication (7)		T	TF	TF7	
Malicious acts (M)	Crime (C)	Organised crime (1)	Smuggling (1)	M	MC	MC1	MC11
			Drugs and weapon arm trade (2)	M	MC	MC1	MC12
			Trafficking (3)	M	MC	MC1	MC13
			Cybercrime (4)	M	MC	MC1	MC14
		Sabotage (2)	Attack against installations (1)	M	MC	MC2	MC21
			Forcible violent protest, "disturbance" (2)	M	MC	MC2	MC22
			Will full plundering (3)	M	MC	MC2	MC23
			Data hacking (4)	M	MC	MC2	MC24
		Espionage (3)	Political (1)	M	MC	MC3	MC31
			Military (2)	M	MC	MC3	MC32
			Industrial (3)	M	MC	MC3	MC33
	Terrorism (T)	Conventional terrorism (1)	Attack against persons (1)	M	MT	MT1	MT11
			Hostage-taking (2)	M	MT	MT1	MT12
			Explosives used against crowds (3)	M	MT	MT1	MT13
			Attack against installations (4)	M	MT	MT1	MT14
		CBRN-terrorism (2)		M	MT	MT2	
	Dysfunctional behaviour (D)	Gangs (1)		M	MD	MD1	
		Individuals (2)		M	MD	MD2	

STOP-IT

STOP-IT